

AUTHENTIC LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL SCIENCE IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS, DIVISION OF BATANGAS CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the assessment of the learning activities availed by junior high school students in earth science, biology, chemistry and physics from selected private secondary schools in the Division of Batangas City. It also looked into the 21st century skills of the students relative to critical thinking/problem solving, creativity, communication and collaboration. Further, profile of teachers was appraised and assessed relationship to the provision of authentic learning activities in science classes. The descriptive method of research was applied in this study with 55 science teachers as respondents. Weighted mean and independent T-test were used for the statistical treatment of gathered data. The study revealed that majority of the science teachers have 1-5 years of teaching experience, finished baccalaureate degree major in science, and actively participated in science-related trainings. It also revealed that students had moderately availed varied learning activities in different science areas. Test of hypothesis revealed significant difference on the students availment of activities in Chemistry when teachers were grouped according to trainings and seminars attended. Further, 21st century skills and competencies were moderately exhibited by the students. From the findings, learning activities demonstrating authenticity were prepared with emphasis on the development of least acquired 21st century skills.

Keywords: science teaching, authentic learning activities, 21st century skills, descriptive research, Philippines